

THE NEED FOR THE ORIGIN, EMERGENCE AND FORMATION OF PEDAGOGICAL TECHNOLOGIES

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ABSTRACT

In the article, the concept of pedagogical technology, its factors of origin, necessity are discussed, and the necessity of its formation is also touched upon.

Keywords: pedagogue, pedagogical technologies, necessity, personnel, education, social attitude.

The second stage of the "National Personnel Training Program" of the Republic of Uzbekistan (1997) is considered the quality stage, in which the need to introduce and master modern pedagogical technologies has been repeated many times, and the need to introduce them to educational institutions has been emphasized. Today, the formation of new social relations in our society, the integration of education into the world education system, the development of democratization and humanization processes require a new approach to modern pedagogical technologies in the educational process.

It is natural to wonder why the interest in pedagogical technology has increased so much today. There are unique methods of pedagogy that have produced many knowledgeable and qualified personnel in our society. Most of the educational community is following this path, but this path cannot serve the society that is striving for independence and the future with the expected results. Because there are certain reasons behind it, namely:

1. The need to use modern pedagogical technologies in order to accelerate and improve the efficiency of population education in order to take a place among developed countries;
2. As a result of the rapid development of science and technology, the size of the information system is increasing;

3. Applying modern techniques and technologies to education, computerization of the educational process, the need to use information technology and technical tools in the educational process;

4. To set the activity of the student and the teacher in the right way, the teacher should know the purpose and content of the education well, he should have mastered the methods, methods and tools of the education, the interest and ambition of the student should be able to direct to the right path;

5. To organize the educational process at a high level and effectively, the teacher must clearly define the goals and tasks, record the educational results in advance, the necessary educational tools to achieve full mastery of the educational subjects, conditions must achieve the conditions of preparation;

6. Creation of the necessary material and technical base for the educational process;

7. Objective and objective evaluation of the results of the educational process, control and evaluation of the process of acquiring knowledge and skills of students has been achieved;

8. The demand for perfect preparation of the growing young generation for life is in such problems as the need to use the principle of a complex approach to objective existence, which is considered the most advanced way of imparting knowledge to them.

Therefore, modern pedagogical technology is an educational event that meets all the requirements of the above conditions.

The essence of the pedagogical technology created in the USA (B. Blum, D. Kratvol, N. Gronland, J. Carroll) in the 60s of the last century and successfully used in the educational system of about 30 countries of the world, its theoretical foundations, special features and the importance of introducing this technology to the education system of our country is very great.

In the middle of the 50s of the last century, an approach to the organization of the educational process in a completely new, unique "technological" way appeared in world pedagogy. In the 60s, it was recognized that the diversity of teaching methods makes it difficult to use them in the organization of the educational process. Therefore, it was necessary to create a common scientific basis for all methods. As a result, the concept of "educational technology" (an Educational technolu) was created. "Pedagogical Technology" magazine was published in the USA in 1961. Also, "Pedagogical technology and educational process" in England (since 1964), "Pedagogical technology" in Japan (since 1965), A similar magazine was published in Italy (since 1971). Since 1971, UNESCO has been publishing the bulletin "Pedagogical

Technologies" of the International Bureau of Education. In the Russian Federation, since 1997, the magazine "School Technologies" has been established.

In addition to foreign specialists, effective scientific and research work is being carried out by pedagogic scientists of our republic, Ashirbaev S., Saidahmedov NS, Jo'raev R., Farberman BL and others.

The reason for the increased interest in pedagogical technology today is that, in developing countries, pedagogical technology has generally been viewed as the main task of educational policy.

This approach was also approved by UNESCO, and in 1972 the International Commission on Educational Development was established. This commission estimated that modern technology is a driving force in the modernization of education.

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